

URANIUM AND THE SPREAD OF CANCER IN IRAQ AFTER THE GULF WAR- A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract: Recently, an increase in the incidence of various cancers has been observed, especially leukemia, lung cancer, breast cancer, which has urged researchers in Iraq to study and find out the causes of the disease, including studying environmental pollution and its impact on the health of the Iraqi individual. In this paper, we present a study reviewing previous studies to determine the extent of the impact of uranium on the Iraqi individual, which examines the possible link between cancer and exposure to uranium. A systematic literature review was conducted through electronic databases due to the use of uranium in many fields in Iraq, including the manufacture of chemical weapons and the ongoing wars to which Iraq is exposed, in addition to the use of household cleaners and pesticides. A large number of studies included in the review indicated the effects of uranium in causing cancer, and some data indicate that exposure to cosmetics, household cleaners, pesticides, and environmental pollution resulting from automobile waste and generators are causes of cancer, as well as fires in oil fields resulting from military actions, causing the release a large quantity of soot and gas are in the atmosphere every day.

1. Introduction

Cancer is a complex disease, and it has only been fully understood over the past decades after the development of new laboratory techniques and diagnostic methods. Although our understanding of the pathophysiology of the disease is improving, little is known about the causes of the disease. A variety of potential risk factors have been proposed so far, including personal habits, lifestyle, and occupational and environmental exposure such as exposure to heavy elements, automobile waste, and generators. The battles and armed confrontations in Iraq from 1988 until 2003 and the subsequent explosions and armed confrontations are one of them. One of the most important causes of environmental pollution in Iraq is that the use of depleted uranium in battles and weapons has a direct impact on human health, especially in increasing of cancer disease.

2. Results

Table (1) shows the scientific results of a number of researches that dealt with studying the effect of uranium on some population of the areas in Iraq affected by a series of wars after the Gulf War, as well as explosions after the year 2003.

Table (1): summarizing of scientific results of a number of researches

No.	Sample	Uranium levels	The reason	Effect	Source
	Blood	Increase of uranium level at cancer patient	Depleted uranium used armed confrontations	Increased incidence case of cancer	Z. Abdelkafi, et al
	Soil	High level of uranium in soil sample	Industrial and military activities	contamination of soil by high level uranium.	A. J. Specht et al.
	Water, soil and hair	Increase of uranium level at cancer patient	Bombardment with uranium weapons	increases and congenital anomaly	S. Alaani, et al.
	Soil and water	Increase of uranium level at cancer patient	Desert Storm in Iraq	Increased breast cancer rate for young girls	A. Faa, et al.
	Breast, kidney, uterus, and stomach tissues	The uranium level in the cancer tissues was higher than control tissues	Continuous explosions in Wars from 1991 to 2003.	Increased incidence case of cancer	A. A. Al-Hamzawi, et al.
	Breast cancer	Uranium levels in breast cancer is larger than control group.	Industrial and military activities	Increased incidence case of cancer	R. S. Ahmed, et al.
	Umbilical cord blood and maternal blood samples	Uranium concentrations blood of deformed infants double larger than normal infants.	High levels of Uranium used in the war	Mortality rate increased at infant in Iraq	M. H. R. Al-Sahlane et al.
	Soil	Fuel fabrication facility was high uranium rat contaminated	Second gulf war in 1991	Excess of the IAEA limits for exemption	Y. M. Z. Al-Bakhat et al
	Animal products and agricultural crops	Reproduce breast cancer in Diyala bridge compared with body organs with 0.0135% rate.	High levels of Uranium used in the war	Increase radiation injuries consequences for genetic with 1850 rate for each one million because irradiation of gonads	H. AL-Tameemi et al.

	Blood	Increase of uranium level at cancer patient	High levels of Uranium used in the war	Increased incidence case of cancer	A. A. Al-Hamzawi, et al.
	Urine	Increase of uranium level at cancer patient	High levels of Uranium used in the war	Increased incidence case of cancer	Z. Q. Rahman, et al.
	Blood, teeth, tissues, urine, and bones	Increase of uranium accumulation level with time pass	High levels of Uranium used in the war	Exceeded the standards levels because uranium level rate accumulation	M. Khudheir et al.
	Teeth and hair samples	Increase uranium levels	Tallil Air Base	Increased congenital anomalies	M. Savabieasfahani, et al.
	Blood	Increase uranium levels	Bombing area by uranium weaponry	Impaired function of immune, cellular immune system damage, and immune cell number is reduced	K. S. Squibb et al.
	Soil and blood	the concentrations in soil samples are higher than the blood concentration samples	Occupations	Occupations and gender play role an increasing the uranium levels.	A. F. Showard et al.

Z. Abdelkafi, et al. Compared the uranium levels between cancer patient and control group in many Iraq governorates such as (Hilla, Baghdad, Basra, Tikrit, Samawah, Kut, Mosul, Maysan, and Nasiriyah). The results show uranium concentration blood samples increase in leukemia disease compared to control people [1]. Items were measured thorium, uranium, arsenic, and lead levels for samples of surface soil in Fallujah governorate by A. J. Specht et al. High level of thorium, uranium, arsenic, and lead were realized in soil samples, on the other hand, can be say contamination of soil by high level of thorium, uranium, arsenic, and lead, this is due to industrial and military activities [2]. S. Alaani, et al. studied the effect of high uranium levels in water and soil and hair of parents your children group with congenital anomalies in Fallujah city, Iraq. Results show that the uranium elements were higher than levels in uncontaminated countries such as Slovenia, Brazil, Japan, and Sweden, As well as, the uranium and mercury levels can be suggest as a possible cause of cancer increases and congenital anomaly [3]. A. Faa, et al. Study the effects of uranium in soil and water on people exposed of the polluted areas after Desert Storm in Iraq. The result showed increased breast cancer rate for young girls. As well as, increase of uranium level blood for patients with leukemia compared to control Iraqi group [4]. A. A. Al-Hamzawi, et al. determined uranium level in breast, kidney, uterus, and stomach tissues for cancer patients in Dhi-Qar, Muthanna and Basrah governorates, where these governorates are exposure to continuous explosions in Wars from 1991 to 2003. The level of uranium in the cancer was larger than control tissues [5]. Uranium blood concentration of females group with breast cancer has been calculated by R. S. Ahmed, et al. and compared this group with control group.

The results show that the levels of uranium in cancer of breast is larger than control group. In addition to, The result show that the mean value of both group has significantly higher comparison with the literature data [6]. M. H. R. Al-Sahlanee et al. Determined the uranium levels in umbilical cord blood and maternal blood samples after delivery in of Basrah, Baghdad, and Dhi-Qar governorates hospitals and in Iraq for woman group with normal delivered and your perfect infants and it is compared with woman group has dead infants and deformed. Uranium concentrations blood of deformed infants double larger than normal infants. As well as, uranium concentrations blood of older pregnant women larger than younger pregnant women. Moreover, uranium concentrations blood in Basrah is larger than Baghdad, and Dhi-Qar governorates. Therefore, mortality rate increased at infant in Iraq due to High levels of Uranium used in the war in umbilical cord and maternal blood [7]. Y. M. Z. Al-Bakhat et al. Study of soil radioactivity activity in fabrication facility of fuel in AL-Tuwaitha site, Baghdad. AL-Tuwaitha site is destroyed at the second gulf war in 1991. The results showed that indicate that the fuel fabrication facility was high uranium rat contaminated in excess of the safty level. [8]. H. AL-Tameemi et al. Study the probability the uranium effected in soil contaminated with uranium due to wars on animal products (meat, egg and milk products) and agricultural crops (vegetables) consumed by humans in Diyala bridge. Reproduce breast cancer in Diyala bridge compared with body organs with 0.0135% rate. As well as increase radiation injuries consequences for genetic with 1850 rate for each one million because irradiation of gonads [9]. A. A. Al-Hamzawi, et al. Studied the levels of blood uranium samples in south of Iraq in Basrah governorate and compare this levels of blood uranium samples in central Iraq Babylon for general people between 1991 and 2003 respectively. The levels of blood uranium samples in Basrah governorate is indicated significant larger according to levels of blood uranium samples Babylon [10]. Z. Q. Rahman, et al. Studied the levels of urine uranium samples in southern Iraq in Al- Diwaniyah governorate for cancer people group and compare this with levels of urine uranium samples control group for both male and female sex. The levels of urine uranium samples in cancer people group is indicated larger according to levels of blood uranium samples of control people group [11]. Analyzed the levels of uranium in blood, teeth, tissues, urine, and bones samples present in people infected by cancer and they are living in southern Iraq in Basrah governorate from 1989 to 2010, by M. Khudheir et al. The result indicated to increase of uranium level with time pass, the smallest value at 1989 and the largest value at 2010, where it is exceeded the standards levels because uranium level rate accumulation with time pass [12]. M. Savabieasfahani, et al. Studied the levels of uranium in deciduous teeth and hair samples for group people with congenital anomalies in Nasiriyah governorate near Tallil Air Base to investigate the effect of uranium on population residential with different distance from Tallil Air Base. Conclusion is increase uranium levels in both deciduous teeth and hair samples in areas around and close to the Tallil Air Base and this increased indicated congenital anomalies , and these distortions decrease as we move away from Tallil Air Base [13]. K. S. Squibb et al. Studied the effect depleted uranium radiation in blood on immune system on group of volunteers in northern Al- Basra governorate about 15 years after bombing area by uranium weaponry and compare volunteers in Baghdad governorate. Chronic exposure to uranium radiation indicated impaired function of immune, cellular immune system damage, and immune cell number is reduced [14]. A. F. Showard et al. Studied the levels of uranium in soil and blood samples in Babylon governorate with different occupations and ages. City center of Babylon found that have highest of uranium levels according to other cities. Moreover, occupations and gender play role an increasing the uranium levels. In addition, the concentrations in soil samples are higher than the blood concentration samples [15].

3. Conclusion

The continuous Wars in Iraq from 1988 to 2003 and after that continuous explosions resulted pollution environmental many of Iraq regions with depleted uranium. The depleted uranium may be affecting the general health people, such as increase in cancers and congenital defects because it has spread widely in the soil, water and air as dust in windstorms. The different types diseases had been showed after Gulf war such

as congenital anomalies and cancer. Increase of the congenital anomalies and cancer is associated with increase of pollution caused by manufacture of chemical weapons and the ongoing wars to which Iraq is exposed. Many data according to Iraqi researchers indicate that, we can conclusion that Faluja, Thi-Qar, Basrah, Mosul and Baghdad are the most damage governorate in Iraq. This systematic review sum out that the contaminated environment in Iraq because continuous wars and series of explosions each Iraqi governorate needs much attention effort to reduce health problems.

4. References

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